

PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF TRAINING INTELLECTUAL QUALITIES
OF TALENTED STUDENTS IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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Abstract. The article deals with the pedagogical system of training intellectual qualities of talented students in academic lyceums. Formation of intellectual qualities of students of academic lyceum, development of an all-round mature person takes place in connection with the formation of their intellectual, physical, moral and scientific outlook.

Key words: pedagogical system, training, intellectual qualities, talented students, academic lyceums, formation, development, intellectual, physical, moral, scientific outlook.

The changes and fundamental reforms taking place in various spheres of social life at the present time are aimed at creating updates in society, increasing the well-being of citizens, and accelerating social development. The basis of these social realities and events, including the problem of forming intellectual and willful character traits of academic lyceum students.

The importance of education plays an important role in the development of intellectual and creative qualities of young people. The essence of the educational process to increase intellectual creative qualities reflects the internal communication and relations that are characteristic of this process and are manifested in certain laws. In the process of developing the intellectual quality of young people, moral skills and skills that benefit the society and correspond to the moral requirements of the individual are formed. To achieve this, the student's mind, worldview and will are systematically influenced. If any of these are

neglected in the process of developing creative potential, it will be difficult to achieve the intended goal.

The current development of society emphasizes the extremely urgent problem of educating a generation with intellectual quality, and it has both national and universal content, its implementation will lead humanity to spirituality and enlightenment, to high perfection and goodness. For this reason, the generation of intellectual quality and solutions to the problem of its formation have been the dream of our people since time immemorial.

The development of intellectual abilities and characteristics of students is not only the formation of independent thinking, but also the explanation that personal thinking plays the main role in development. The intellectual ability of students is not created by itself. In order to develop this ability, it is necessary to learn and master creative thinking, to develop conclusions, thanks to which learners and students gradually acquire skills and become future specialists. In order to lead students' learning and mental activity in the right direction, pedagogues should be independent thinkers and experienced people. In order to effectively develop students' intellectual abilities, they must have a sufficient amount of knowledge, only then they will have the ability to think comprehensively and draw correct conclusions. In addition, it is necessary for students to have mental ability, because with the help of mental ability, deep knowledge is learned, and naturally, the ability to think creatively and independently is also formed and developed.

The genesis of the formation of feelings of love, inclination, curiosity for learning and education in a person begins from early childhood. The formation of intellectual and willful qualities of character in early adolescence makes him mature as a person. This issue requires, first of all, to pay serious attention to the potential of personnel, to properly organize the future specialist's professional

training and attitude to mastering the profession based on the socio-economic requirements of society's development.

From this point of view, it is possible to ensure the stability of development only by paying serious attention to the process of personality formation in each student, especially to the formation of intellectual and voluntary qualities in his character. In our opinion, the topic acquires important socio-pedagogical importance with its following aspects:

1. The formation of intellectual qualities in academic lyceum students has the characteristic of activating them in market economy relations.

2. Formation of intellectual qualities in students improves personality.

If we look at the past of the Uzbek people, our ancestors always paid attention to improving the intellectual abilities of young people, and it was their constant dream. Achieving such a dream was the main goal of not only the head of the family or trainers in educational institutions, but also the sages-intellectuals of our country (scientists, poets, writers, historians, hadith scholars, etc.) and just rulers.

Formation of modern qualities of intellectual ability in students of academic lyceum ensures the harmony of the past and the present, creates a social order based on the demand of the time. The use of intellectual qualities and their full realization, and the determination of specific social perspectives on this basis, is one of the urgent tasks of every state, society and people. After all, it is inevitable that every person, as a component of society and nation, should realize himself, develop himself, and mature. Some difficulties and complications in the manifestation of character traits are especially noticeable during the student years, and such a social situation affects the further development of a person. All this confirms the need for a deep, comprehensive and serious study of the personality of academic lyceum students, and at the same time, in the conditions where a new system of social relations is being established, it is necessary to use

all available opportunities for the formation of intellectual and volitional characteristics of educational subjects.

It is known that in order to achieve such a goal, the system of continuous education requires regular implementation and monitoring of reforms, especially in academic lyceums. In the implementation of this activity, the following should be considered:

- to fundamentally improve the personnel potential of the educational system, to increase the professional prestige of the educator, teacher, teacher and researcher;

- development of various types of state and non-state educational institutions;

- structural restructuring of the continuing education system: radical change of educational and professional programs taking into account the modern achievements of education, science, technology and technology, economy and culture;

- broad assimilation of advanced technologies and creation of new ones, structural changes in the economy, expansion of the scope of foreign investments, including training, retraining and upgrading of management system personnel;

- to develop and implement measures to strengthen the role of family, parents, public organizations, neighborhoods, charity and international funds in education, as well as moral, intellectual and physical upbringing of young people;

- creation and introduction of a system for evaluating the quality of the educational process and personnel training;

- development and implementation of excellent mechanisms of integration of science and practice of continuous education system;

- expanding and developing cooperation with foreign and international organizations in education, science, etc.

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